

Islam, Prejudiced Western Fiction and Islamic Feminism

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Abstract:

Colonial narratives about Islam and Muslims are filled with prejudices. The depiction of Islamic religion and Muslim societies in a generally negative and self-serving ways is likewise the consequence of experiences between Western development and Islam. The Western English fiction venture Muslims as suggestive, crude, oblivious, monsters and slave dealers. It was a colonial mindset, but this is also a fact that this trend has been intensified since 9/11, obviously due to the satanic acts of a group falsely projecting itself as the true representative of Islam. That is the reason that most of the fiction writers who somehow or the other make Islam and Muslims their main theme, utilize the terms, for example, fear mongers, maniacs, fundamentalists, and savage for Muslims. Colonial theories and histories wedded with actions of some Islamist groups have been wrongly used to portray Islam and Muslims, especially the condition of women in Islam or Muslim societies, in a negative manner by the fiction writers.

A group of scholars has challenged these narratives along with the misdeeds of its own people. The Islamic Feminists have not only challenged these prejudiced notions rich in racial supremacy, they have attacked those traditions of scholarship too which helped in portraying Islam and women in a negative manner. Their discourse is helping a new form fiction written by Muslim authors wherein Islam is the central theme. This paper tries to locate different aspects of prejudiced Western fiction, Islamic Feminist discourses and the rise of a fiction which is against the traditional Islamic interpretations and the Western approach regarding Muslims.

Keywords: Islam in English Fiction; Muslims in English Fiction; Islamic Feminism.

The Prejudiced Narrative

Literature interested in religious themes has always been part of the canon of literary traditions around the world, and English literature is no exception in this regard. But with regard to Islam and Muslims, it is generally observed that the Western narratives and media conceptualize them with the drastic effect which scars the Western people, and consequently, helps in creating a world view of Muslims as they want to be. The media plays a very powerful role in molding viewers' perception on reality. References to Islam and Prophet Mohammad (Peace be Upon Him) throughout English literature reveal ignorance and prejudice.

The distorted images and fabricated views which typically characterize the Western representation of the Islamic creeds and Muslims with reference to some particular incidents are found in the English narratives of the East as well. The portrayal of Islamic religion and Muslim cultures in a largely negative and self-serving ways is also the result of encounters between Western civilization and Islam. The Western English narratives project them as erotic, primitive, ignorant, beasts and slave traders. Since 9/11 the situation has worsened. These narratives use the terms such as terrorists, lunatics, fundamentalists, and blood-thirsty for Muslims.

This dangerous trend of literary creativity has further widened the gap between Muslims and the world community. The books like *Among the Believers* and *Beyond Belief* (by V. S. Naipaul) are being hailed as "new levels of understanding about Islam". Edward Said puts it best in his book *Covering Islam* when he says:

The term "Islam" as it is used today seems to mean one simple thing but in fact is part fiction, part ideological label, part minimal designation of a religion called Islam. In no real significant way is there a direct correspondence between the "Islam" in common Western usage and the enormously varied life that goes on within the world of Islam, with its more than 800,000,000 [now 1.3 billion] people, its millions of square miles of territory principally in Africa and Asia, its dozens of societies, states, histories, geographies, cultures. On the other hand, "Islam" is peculiarly traumatic news today in the West... During the past few years, especially since events in Iran caught European and American attention so strongly, the media have therefore covered Islam: they have portrayed it, characterized it, analyzed it, given instant courses on it, and consequently they have made it "known" ⁽¹⁾.

Naipaul didn't dare mentioning that all that had been made "known" was not Islam but a biased understanding of Islam. This phenomenon of demonizing Islam and Muslims was a colonial agenda, and the world fall prey to it. Islam and Muslim have been of late a topic of discussion amongst Western scholars and media, and the images and discourses related to them tend often to

be negative. However, the portrayal of Islam and Muslims has never been as heavily demonized and marginalized in Western discourses as in the post 9/11 era, when they are being also represented as the sources of fear and threat. According to Dr. Jack. G. Shaheen, the world's foremost authority on media images of Arabs and Muslims, American cinema has been demonizing Arabs and Muslims more than any other people since long before the events of 9/11. Shaheen argues that the only image of the Arab world that the majority of Americans encounter is the Hollywood version, and this is almost without exception simplistic and negative. Amongst a large number of literatures written on this theme, based on the study of more than 900 films, *Reel bad Arabs: how Hollywood vilifies a people* ⁽²⁾, by Shaheen shows how moviegoers are led to believe that all Arabs are Muslims and all Muslims are Arabs. The moviemakers' distorted lenses have shown Arabs as heartless, brutal, uncivilized, religious fanatics through common depictions of Arabs kidnapping or raping a fair maiden; expressing hatred against the Jews and Christians; and demonstrating a love for wealth and power. Interestingly all these were the colonial traits. They were afraid of the Muslims because they knew that Europe was a stronghold of Muslim rulers, and that they have lived as subject for long. Therefore, they tried their best to demonize Islam, Muslims and the Muslim states. It was a kind of psychological war against Islam. They used colonialism as a weapon to target Islam.

A British Academy postdoctoral research fellow at Oxford, Dr. Wendy O'Shea-Meddour⁽³⁾, has offered a revisionist reading of Naipaul's Islamic travel narratives in her epoch-making research, *Gothic Horror and Muslim Madness in V. S. Naipaul's Beyond Belief: 'Orientalist' Excursions among the Converted People*. She argues that Islamophobia has been disturbingly misinterpreted as expertise. Focusing on three main literary themes – nineteenth-century literary conventions, the gothic genre, and neurosis – she has exposed this bigoted worldview and called for Naipaul's status to be reconsidered.

Western constructions are also contested and challenged by intellectuals, academicians and scholars in what has come to be one of the defining 21st century issues: Fred Halliday's "Islamophobia Reconsidered" (1999), Noam Chomsky's *The Culture of Terrorism* (1999), Ziauddin Sardar and Meryll Wyn Davies' *Why Do People Hate America?* (2002), John E. Richardson's *(Mis)Representing Islam: The Racism and Rhetoric of British Broadsheet Newspapers* (2004), Samir Kassir's *Being Arab* (2006), Robert Fisk's *The*

Great War for Civilisation: The Conquest of the Middle East (2007), or Tabish Khair's *Muslim Modernities* (2008) display, *inter alia*, multifarious approaches to this issue.

The Wall Street Journal editorial, *You Still Can't Write About Muhammad*, started the world-wide controversy over the book, *The Jewel of Medina*, written by Sherry Jones on the life of Hazrat A'isha (wife of the Prophet). This is the novel that has been characterized as "soft core pornography" by Islamic studies professor Denise Spielberg. This trend of representing Muslims in a negative manner even in the novels written before 9/11 has widely been debated by the scholars of international repute.

Though Indian English fiction writers have never been as harsh as their Bengali or Hindi counterparts, but the writers like Rushdie and Naipaul, who, anyhow, have Indian connections, have been a part of this hate-generating fiction writing. India, being a multicultural state, has witnessed innumerable cultural clashes. Based on a review of English fiction and the multicultural social set up of India, we observe that the scholars of Indian origin have also taken an active part in this discourse. Undeniably, the traits attributed to the Muslims in most of English fiction are a reality in certain parts of the Muslim world and among certain Muslim people; however, to consider the English fiction's representation of Islam and Muslims as a mirror or a reflection of reality is inaccurate.

The debate and discourses on Muslim issues heavily rely on the theme of sexuality, women rights and fundamentalism. There are some sane voices that need to be heard for a fair understanding of the Muslim issues for humane and humanized understanding of Islam and Muslims. It will help in narrowing the widening gap between Muslim and non-Muslim worlds.

Counter Narrative

An honest debate on these issues will definitely make at least three contributions to the areas of discourses on the representations of Islam and Muslims in the context of modern English Fiction. First, it will contribute to the truth of the expanding knowledge base of self-directed exploration of Islam and Muslims in modern English fiction. Second, it will be an attempt to participate in the world-wide debate on the concept of projecting 'other' culture as a critical factor behind the post 9/11 English fiction, and the emergence of Muslim narratives and the discourse of English. Finally, the ultimate issue underlying

such debate will be religious ideology and cultural fantasy that keep the fiction writers of English fascinating about the half truth of a particular religious group.

It is observed that besides the novels are some other novels that reiterate the account of Islam as a backward and misogynist religion. They also portray Muslim women as powerless victims of Islam. There is a long list of such novels but mention may be made of the novels like *Beyond Belief* by V.S. Naipaul, *Midnight's Children*, and *The Satanic Verses* by Salman Rushdie, *The Heart of Darkness* by Joseph Conrad, *Vathek* by William Beckford, *American Gods* by Neil Gaiman, *Archangel Protocol series* by Lyda Morehouse, *Budayeen Nights* by George Alec Effinger, *Coyote Kings of the Space Age Bachelor Pad* by Minister Faust, *Edenborn* by Nick Sagan, *Ender's Game* by Orson Scott Card, *Evolution* by Stephen Baxter, *Fool's Game* by Sarah Zettel, *Harry Potter series* by JK Rowling, *Effendi and Felaheen* by John Courtney Grimwood, *Stand on Zanzibar* by John Brunner, *Strangers in a Strange Land* by Robert A. Heinlein, *The Mote in God's Eye*, and *The Gripping Hand* by Larry Niven and Jerry Pournell, *Bury The Unreasoning Mask* by Philip Jose Farmer, *A Wind In Cairo* by Judith Tarr, *The Years of Rice and Salt* by Kim Stanley, *The Jewel of Medina* by Sherry Jones, *Alamut* by Vladimir Bartol, *The Blood of Flowers* by Anita Amirrezvani, *Haj* by Leon Uris, *The Historian* by Elizabeth Kostova, *Snares* by Katherine Kerr, *Where She was Standing* by Maggie Helwig, etc. Most of these novels are based more on stereotyping than on empirical research. Whereas Monica Ali (*Brick Lane*), Samina Ali (*Madras on Rainy Days*), Aman Tahmina (*A Golden Age*), Uzma Aslam Khan (*Tresspassing*), Fadia Faqir (*My Name is Salma*), Azadeh Moaveni (*Lipstick Jihad*), Leila Aboulela (*The Translator*), Khaled Hosseini (*The Kite Runner*; *A Thousand Splendid Suns*) explicitly explore the engagement of Muslim characters with the sacred through Islamic rituals and practices, and emphasize the importance of the form of religious rituals and symbols. They also suggest that personal spiritual experiences of Muslims are not dissimilar to those of people of other creeds. Some of these novels are treated as examples of Islamic Feminism. These novels may be seen as countering not only the colonial mentality, the patriarchal set up of the Muslim society as well.

We need to initialize and propagate this discourse as it will be an addition to the literature on cultural conflicts and cross-cultural study of religion and literature, and thus it will play an

important role in creating social harmony in its global context.

There is a need to study and evaluate these novels textually to analyze the cross-cultural discourses, in order to explore the notion of the Muslim sacred and its representation in contemporary English fiction along with the Muslim-English fiction (*Muslim Narratives*). If one evaluates the trends of dialogue and harmony besides clash and hegemony between civilizations, inherent in these novels, by drawing on the political and cultural contexts of these narratives and on the plurality of voices articulated in the texts, he will have to focus on the points that 1) Why did most of the fiction writers of English represent Islamic culture and Muslim characters in a negative way. a) What are the factors that generated the "Fear of the Green Menace"? b) To what extent 9/11 is responsible in promoting a deep-rooted hatred in Islam and Muslims in a number of Hollywood motion pictures and English fiction. 2) Did religious rules regarding sexual practices, veiling, seclusion, and women's mobility in the public sphere affect the fictional narratives? 3) Are there any indications of a non-prejudiced trend of fiction writing in English? 4) To what extent did the discourses by Muslim and non-Muslim scholars had an effect on the cross-cultural debates?

Reform from within: Islamic Feminism and Fiction writing

The representation of the Islam and Muslims is offered in various ways in these texts. There are deliberations and disseminations on Muslim religiosity, Muslim fundamentalism, Muslim terrorism, Muslim sexuality, Muslim homosexuality, and Muslim women issues. This is an undeniable fact that some interpretative traditions of Islamic texts made rooms for such harsh criticism.

It is noteworthy that the rise of Islamic Feminism has resulted in a rich and pathbreaking discourse on almost all the issues raised by the prejudiced fiction writers or historians or so-called social reformers of the colonial era who left no stone unturned in dehumanizing Islamic culture for establishing their own hybrid culture. It has challenged the prejudiced notions of the traditional exegesis as well. As a result of these efforts, organizations that are not Islamists, or are not directly involved in Islamic feminism are also raising their voices for rights based on its intellectual rhetoric. An example of this can be seen in Pakistan, where the Women's March made good use of their ideas. The Arab Spring may also be served as an example of this awakening. There

were many demonstrations of women in Turkey, Iran, Egypt, Malaysia and Africa that directly attacked the government or the empire for its patriarchal mindset. Even in Afghanistan, at the intellectual level, its effects are beginning to show. The biggest benefit of this is that women scholars engaged in different fields of study are now opposing the Islamic laws based on the prejudiced male interpretations. They are also challenging the colonial rhetoric regarding Islam and women.

A study of the rhetoric of Islamic feminists, as well as the views of women intellectuals who support the new interpretation of the Qur'an makes it clear that they all speak the same language. Their areas of interest are focused on some important issues, which can also be called a joint venture of the Islamic feminists. They believe that the Holy Qur'an does not allow the formation of a patriarchal society, nor does it command motherhood. The message of the Qur'an is that there is no gender difference between men and women, except the biological needs, and that both are responsible for their own deeds as servants of God, and whoever of them is pious is beloved by Allah.

In view of the *imams* (religious leaders) and scholars who have written commentaries on the Holy Qur'an, interfaith (Qur'an, *Hadith*, *Sunnah*) as well as external factors have always been involved in elaborating women's rights, their sexuality, their family and social status. There have been tribes, regions, political needs as well as preconceived notions which were incorporated in formulating laws. For example, Islamic family law (*'aqli qawaneen*) has never been completely dependent on the Qur'an and *Sunnah*. Some of the verses have been studied by male commentators in such a way that it highlights the non-Qur'anic meaning of the patriarchal aspect and the total authority of men over women. Polygamy and divorce have been made the right of men, while the Qur'an commands to avoid it as much as possible. Based on a few individual verses of the Holy Qur'an and sometimes just a few words, such *Shari'ah* rules were promulgated which were reserved for women only, while in essence, they apply to both men and women. An example at hand is the discourse on the commentaries of the verses of *Surah An-Nisa* (*Women*) of the Holy Qur'an wherein no distinction has been made between a wife and a slave. Although the Qur'an does not even suggest such interpretations. Despite acknowledging the services of women in the promotion of Islam and religious studies, conscious efforts were made to keep them away from scholarly pursuits. During the Abbasids and Umayyads women were considered a mere

object of sexual pleasure. More importance was given to those *surahs* and *hadiths* which could prove that women are inferior to men and such Qur'anic verses and *hadiths* were ignored in which there are clear orders regarding all kinds of equality between men and women.

Contrary to the injunctions of the Holy Qur'an regarding marriage, polygamy, divorce, *halala*, *kaniz*, *zina*, *hadd*, etc., such laws were formulated on the basis of which men could have powers over women. Such types of marriage were invented which were aimed at the sexual exploitation of women and gratification of men's lust. Some commentaries also relied on Jewish and Christian traditions to promote sexual harassment and sexual prejudice, and conscious efforts were made to keep the woman's sexuality and her body under the control of man. Attempts were also made to gradually remove the respect and status that women enjoyed during the Prophet's life from the influence of tribal traditions, and women's religious, social and economic responsibilities during the Prophet's life were also reduced over time.

Furthermore, in their discourses on the feminine interpretation of the Qur'an, feminine theology, Islamic feminism, etc., all these intellectuals have given a reasoned answer to the prejudices of the West towards Islam and Muslims in the light of the Holy Qur'an and the Islamic theological traditions. Similarly, some have refuted the notion that patriarchy is in the blood of the Arabs and have made it clear that the link with non-Islamic traditions was distorting the true teachings of Islam. For this reason, Islamic feminism has been considered a global trend for both Muslims and non-Muslims.

Certainly, the rulings and decisions regarding women that are present in our historical and traditional jurisprudence and *fatwas* (rulings based on Islamic laws) sometimes feel surprisingly un-Islamic. Scholars like Asma Barlas, Ziba Mir-Husseini, Amina Wadud, Oaima Abu-Bakr, Leila Ahmed, Azizah al-Hibri, Kecia Ali, Mei Yamani, Ayesha Hidayatullah, etc., have presented various examples to prove that after the Prophet (Peace be Upon Him) the Islamic exegetics have made good use of prejudices. But, thankfully, those interpretations have little effect on Muslim society today. But of course, there is a group of *ulemas* (scholars of Islamic texts) everywhere in the world which is inclined towards propagating such interpretations simply to keep a hold on the society. There are various examples from Egypt, Lebanon, Turkey, Malaysia, etc., which amply prove that the

illiterate Muslim mass had always been controlled by clerics and *imams* who themselves do not have adequate knowledge about the teachings of Islam. The situation had been similar in the subcontinent. On the one hand there was a group of highly educated theologians who were engaged in writing and composing Islamic interpretative texts while on the other hand there were groups who kept misleading the illiterate Muslim people in villages and towns just to bake their own bread. These *maulvis* never had a correct understanding of the religion, nor were they well acquainted with the world system of Islam. In such a case, the subcontinent, despite being a respectable center for Islamic scholarship, has not been able to do significant work on the ground. Obviously, such kind of interpretation among the middle or lower middle class is not useful for ordinary Muslims but for those who are determined on misinterpreting Islam.

The Islamic feminist commentators, or the intellectuals who support the re-interpretation of Islamic texts, have tried to distance themselves from the traditional exegesis by adopting their own method of interpretation. But their method of interpretation in fact follows the traditions of the exegesis of the Holy Qur'an. For example, the method adopted by Asma Barlas, Amina Wadud or Rifat Hassan emphasizes the need to understand and interpret the Holy Qur'an only through the Holy Qur'an. This is not a new method or a method specific to these scholars. Allama Ibn Taymiyyah also insisted on this for understanding the Qur'an. Allama Ibn Katheer had said that understanding the text of the Qur'an from the Qur'an itself is the best method to interpret the Qur'an. And if the interpretation of the Qur'an is not found in the Qur'an, then one should refer to the *Sunnah*, because the *Sunnah* is in itself the interpretation of the Qur'an. Asma Barlas (4), Rifat Hassan (5), Amina Wadud (6), etc. have adopted the same method of commentary, and they have demanded that the Holy Qur'an be recited as a whole. They

believe that for specific matters, especially for women and the family system, instead of a single verse, all the verses related to these matters should be studied in the Holy Qur'an. Rifat Hassan wrote that Muslims should read everything that the Qur'an says on any subject. She insists that one must not try to define his / her meaning by separating a piece or part of a verse from the text, because the Qur'an is a very comprehensive and coherent scripture. Asma Barlas, in her commentary on the Holy Qur'an, said that she prefers to study the Holy Qur'an in her quest for women's rights. From her retrieval of the Holy Qur'an, it is clear that it is not just secularism's special distinction to talk about women's rights, nor is it that talking about it from an Islamic point of view is secular Islamization. Presenting a study of all the major Islamic feminists engaged in the feminist understanding of *hadiths*, she expressed the view that in the interpretive process of Islamic feminists, the Holy Qur'an is always being considered for inter-textual study. They focus on the language, rhetoric and linguistic terminology of the Holy Qur'an. Instead of individual study of a verse, an attempt is made to keep in view all the verses related to a subject.

In fact, these are the voices of contemporary intellectuals that demand to be heard because, regardless of the mood of the commentaries, laws related to the relationship of men and women, and the family laws that have been framed on the basis of them violate the rights of women. It is not surprising to find that this theoretical discourse is paving ways for a new kind of fiction which is being written by the Arabs and some Western writers in Arabic and English. Novels and short stories written by the writers like Assia Djebar, Leila Aboulela, Hannan Al-Sheikh, Fadia Faqir, Mohja Kahf, etc. are very promising due to the reason that they are fighting a two-front war, decolonializing the myths about Islam and women, and demystifying patriarchal interpretative traditions of Islam.

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